

DELIVERABLE

D.4.1.1 REVIEW OF EXISTING COURSES FOR THE ASSESSMENT OF THE STATE OF CONSCIOUSNESS AFTER CAS IN BROILER AND TURKEYS

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1. Introduction

The aim of sub-activity 4.1 was to evaluate the existing training courses for poultry welfare assessment (broilers and turkeys). It consisted of a description of existing courses and materials including information on objectives, content and training materials as well as an identification of the gaps that the Centre might address in the future. EURCAW-Poultry-SFA aims to review and assess the existing training courses and materials in use at Better Training for Safer Food (BTSF), or at other levels (*e.g.*, national and regional training courses).

Assessment of the state of consciousness after stunning is required in Council Regulation (EC) No 1099/2009 of 24 September 2009 on the protection of animals at the time of killing. This deliverable contains an approach of the content of both BTSF and EU National training for the priority area related to the state of consciousness after controlled atmosphere stunning (CAS) of broilers and turkeys. BTSF (https://ec.europa.eu/chafea/food/index_en.htm) is an initiative of the European Commission aimed at organising and developing an EU training strategy in several areas including the animal welfare. Training is designed for staff of Competent Authorities of EU Member States involved in official control activities with the objective of keeping them updated with all aspects of Community law to ensure that controls are carried out in a more harmonized, objective and conveniently in all Member States. The training is conducted in English.

Within the BTSF Programme, training and education are key parameters and the expected outcomes are:

- To promote an integrated and global approach to the legislation.
- To increase competence and expertise of controlling authorities, imposing high standards on control officials in the Member States.
- To encourage a harmonized approach to EU and national control systems.
- To spread knowledge and awareness of EU law in the specific fields.

Besides BTSF, National training is also carried out. While BTSF is the training for the EU Member States trainers, the National training is intended for the official veterinarians of the related Member State. In this sense, it might imply slight differences from the EU legislation in animal welfare corresponding to the transcription of directives into national laws, with a specific way of implementation. Moreover, National trainings are conducted in the official languages of the Member States.

Thus, EURCAW-Poultry-SFA collected the related BTSF trainings and requested the National training materials to all the EU Member States. The Centre received feedback from seven Member States. However, four of them pointed out the absence of national training course about this topic, so at the end we only received and revised the training from Italy, France and Spain.

2. Methodology used

BTSF syllabus and training material from 2011 to 2021 related to the topic were obtained and reviewed. BTSF courses include not only the theoretical lectures but also practical cases and general discussion. However, this deliverable only considers the theoretical lectures. A summary of the BTSF courses reviewed specifying the year, the number of editions, and the countries where the training took place, is shown in Table 1. For additional information of BTSF content per editions see Annex I. It should be highlighted that the main goal

of the BTSF courses have remained along the past editions, but their content has been slightly modified according to the scientific updates and due to different lecturers.

Table 1. General information about the BTSF courses editions revised related to slaughter in poultry.

Title/topic	Year	Num. of editions	Location
Animal welfare at poultry slaughter	2011	1	Spain
	2013-2014	2	Spain and Italy
	2016	1	Spain
Animal welfare at poultry slaughter (advanced level)	2018	1	Germany
Animal welfare at slaughter and in killing for disease control	2012	1	Spain
	2014	2	Spain and Italy
	2015	1	Italy
Animal Welfare at slaughter and killing for disease control for poultry	2022	1	e-learning

Furthermore, several National training course materials related to the assessment of the state of consciousness after CAS were also revised. A summary of these reviewed courses specifying the EU member state, the year and the general content of the training is shown in Table 2. For additional information of National training content per editions see Annex II.

Table 2. General information about the National training courses revised related to the state of consciousness after CAS in poultry.

Title/topic	Year	Num. of editions	Location
Stunning by CO2 method	2018	1	Spain
Animal welfare indicators for the slaughter of poultry and rabbits	2020	1	Spain
Practical examples of animal welfare at slaughter	2021	1	Spain
Animal protection in slaughterhouses for poultry and rabbits and associated official controls	2020	1	France (e-learning)
Protection of animals at slaughter and killing – regulation 1099: basic course for chief scientific officers	2019	1	Italy

Training material was revised in detail to evaluate at which extent is covering the main welfare concerns related to suboptimal CAS procedure (*i.e.*, aversive behaviours during induction to unconsciousness, failure in induction to unconsciousness and recovery of consciousness before death). Moreover, information regarding the frequency and distribution of the checks of the animals and how to do the sampling of animals was also revised (as required in Council Regulation (EC) No 1099/2009). Lectures addressing specifically the topic of CAS for broiler or turkey were identified and assessed to which extent describe the animal-, the resource- and the management-based indicators (ABIs, RBIs, MBIs, respectively) that needs training.

For this purpose, each indicator was scored according to the coverage level found in the training material as follows:

0 = indicator “not covered” as there was no evidence to be mentioned in any lecture of the training material reviewed.

1 = indicator “partially covered” as it was mentioned in training material but without evidence of detailed description of the methodology (*i.e.*, found in text).

2 = indicator “well covered” as it was mentioned in the training material and with evidence of detailed description of the methodology and assessment (*i.e.*, found in text along with audio-visual support such as photography or videos, or case studies).

3. Assessment of the training material

The lectures from BTSF and national training courses were analyzed, and the coverage of the welfare indicators were scored. It should be highlighted that trainings are always addressed for poultry but not specie specific (*i.e.* broiler chickens or turkeys).

ABIs for identification of aversion during induction to unconsciousness are not covered neither in any of the BTSF editions nor in any national training courses (table 3).

Table 3. Coverage scores of the selected animal-based indicators (ABIs), for the assessment of aversion during induction to unconsciousness in CAS in broilers and turkeys from the revised BTSF and National training material.

Welfare issue	Indicator	Type of indicator	Training material, year	Coverage score
Aversion during induction to unconsciousness	Head shaking	ABI	BTSF (2011 to 2022)	0
			France (2020)	0
			Italy (2019)	0
			Spain (18, 20, 21)	0
	Wing flapping	ABI	BTSF (2011 to 2019)	0
			BTSF (2022)	1
			France (2020)	0
			Italy (2019)	0
	Mandibulation	ABI	BTSF (2011 to 2022)	0
			France (2020)	0
			Italy (2019)	0
			Spain (18, 20, 21)	0
	Jumping	ABI	BTSF (2011 to 2022)	0
			France (2020)	0
			Italy (2019 ab)	0
			Spain (18, 20, 21)	0
Gasping or respiratory disruption	ABI	BTSF (2011 to 2019)	0	
		BTSF (2022)	1	
		France (2020)	0	
		Italy (2019)	0	
			Spain (18, 20, 21)	0

The indicators to assess failure at inducing unconsciousness and recovery of consciousness before death after CAS are shown in Table 4 and 5, respectively. These indicators are not covered in most of the BTSF trainings. In this sense, it is only addressed in 2013-2014 edition and the 2022 e-learning edition. BTSF 2013-2014 put attention in ABIs for the assessment of the state of consciousness in poultry after CAS, and it seems to be a

consequence of the EFSA report (2013a). National training materials from Italy (2019b) and France (2020b) also includes this information. However, in all cases the training mentions the ABIs but not their descriptions and apparently, there is no audio-visual material (photos or videos) linked. Hence, the ABIs are considered partially covered in all of them.

Table 4. Coverage scores of the selected animal-based indicators (ABIs) for the assessment of failure in inducing unconsciousness after CAS in broilers and turkeys from the revised BTSF and National training material.

Welfare issue	Indicator	Type of indicator	Training material, year	Coverage score
Failure in inducing unconsciousness	Muscle tone	ABI	BTSF (2013-14)	1
			BTSF (11-12, 15-16, 18-19, 22)	0
			France (2020)	1
			Italy (2019)	1
			Spain (18, 20, 21)	0
	Breathing	ABI	BTSF (2013-14)	1
			BTSF (11-12, 15-16, 18-19, 22)	0
			France (2020)	1
			Italy (2019)	1
			Spain (18, 20, 21)	0
	Wing flapping	ABI	BTSF (2013-14)	1
			BTSF (11-12, 15-16, 18-19, 22)	0
			France (2020)	1
			Italy (2019)	1
			Spain (18, 20, 21)	0
	Spontaneous blinking	ABI	BTSF (2013-14)	1
			BTSF (11-12, 15-16, 18-19, 22)	0
			France (2020)	1
			Italy (2019)	1
			Spain (18, 20, 21)	0
Corneal or palpebral reflex	ABI	BTSF (2013-14)	1	
		BTSF (11-12, 15-16, 18-19, 22)	0	
		France (2020)	1	
		Italy (2019)	1	
		Spain (18, 20, 21)	0	
Vocalisation	ABI	BTSF (2013-14)	1	
		BTSF (11-12, 15-16, 18-19, 22)	0	
		France (2020)	1	
		Italy (2019)	1	
		Spain (18, 20, 21)	0	

Other training courses address CAS in a more general approach, like BTSF (2022 e-learning), Spain (2018, 2020 and 2021), Italy (2019b) and France (2020b); *i.e.* general description of the system, legal key parameters, or critical control points.

Table 5. Coverage scores of the selected animal-based indicators (ABIs) and management-based Indicators (MBIs) for the assessment of the recovery of consciousness before death after CAS in broilers and turkeys from the revised BTSF and National training material.

Welfare issue	Indicator	Type of indicator	Training material, year	Coverage score
Recovery of consciousness before death	Wing flapping	ABI	BTSF (2013-14, 22)	1
			BTSF (11-12, 15-16, 18-19)	0
			France (2020)	1
			Italy (2019)	1
			Spain (18, 20, 21)	0
	Muscle tone	ABI	BTSF (2013-14, 22)	1
			BTSF (11-12, 15-16, 18-19)	0
			France (2020)	1
			Italy (2019)	1
			Spain (2020)	1
	Spain (18, 21)	0		
	Breathing	ABI	BTSF (2013-14, 22)	1
			BTSF (11-12, 15-16, 18-19)	0
			France (2020)	1
			Italy (2019)	1
Spain (2020)			1	
Spain (18, 21)	0			
Corneal or palpebral reflex	ABI	BTSF (2013-14, 22)	1	
		BTSF (11-12, 15-16, 18-19)	0	
		France (2020)	1	
		Italy (2019)	1	
		Spain (2020)	1	
Spain (18, 21)	0			
Checks	Frequency and distribution of the checks	MBI	BTSF (2013-14)	2
			BTSF (11-12, 15-16, 22)	0
			BTSF (2018-19)	1
			France (2020)	2
			Italy (2019)	0
	Spain (18, 20, 21)	0		
	Representative and sufficient sample of animals	MBI	BTSF (2013-14)	2
			BTSF (11-12, 15-16, 18-19, 22)	0
			France (2020)	2
			Italy (2019)	0
Spain (18, 20, 21)			0	

On the other hand, the indicators should be assessed on a representative sample size. The frequency and distribution in which the official veterinarians should do these checks is lacking in most of the training materials. In BTSF, only the 2014 edition included the calculation of the sample size, but it was removed in the following editions. However, France is nowadays fully covering the description of the sample size, representative and frequency of sampling.

Gaps that the centre could possibly address in the future

ABIs for the welfare requirements related to the state of consciousness (failure of inducing consciousness and recovery of consciousness before death) are currently not covered in most of the training courses, or partially covered when the ABIs from EFSA report (2013a) are described. However, ABIs for the assessment of aversion during induction to unconsciousness are missing in all the training material reviewed. Thus, it is necessary to put attention especially on these welfare requirements for a more complete training, and to provide some graphic material to complement the definitions.

Some of the ABIs related to the state of consciousness are the same for different stunning systems (*i.e.* breathing, spontaneous blinking, corneal or palpebral reflex, wing flapping, head shaking), meaning that examples of them are sometimes included when discussing waterbath stunning (see [EURCAW-Poultry-SFA – 2020–D4.1.1](#) for coverage scores), but they are not explained in detail for CAS with photos or videos, neither for different poultry species. However, EURCAW-Poultry-SFA is currently working on a study using different gas mixtures for CAS in broilers in order to assess the prevalence and length of indicators of aversion during the induction phase, the prevalence of indicators of the state of consciousness at the end of the CAS process to unconsciousness and the efficiency of stunning according to the CAS key parameters. The report of this study will be delivered at the end of 2022.

In order to assess the welfare of broilers and turkeys during CAS, it is essential to assess ABIs in a representative sample of sufficient size any time there is a change in the slaughtering (*e.g.*, specie, size of the animals, etc) having possibly an effect on stunning efficiency. However, training on how to calculate the sample size and which animal should be selected at which frequency is usually missing in BTSF courses and, probably, a gap in most of the national trainings. In this sense, this should be taken into consideration, and it could be possibly addressed by EURCAW-Poultry-SFA in the future.

4. Conclusions

- 1) Training courses on poultry welfare at the slaughterhouse exist in BTSF and at National level in some Members States. However, the number of National trainings courses that EURCAW-Poultry-SFA received for revision was scarce and a complete picture of the training activities in the EU is not possible to draw.
- 2) Animal-based indicators of welfare related to CAS is a specific topic that is partially covered in most of the lectures reviewed. However, it is always addressed for poultry but not specie specific.
- 3) It is worthy to note that sometimes, specific indicators for welfare assessment were addressed in certain editions of BTSF that were removed in the following ones probably due to different authors in charge of the presentation. In this sense, it could be pertinent to catch up some past lectures for future editions. On the other hand, sometimes training from Member States offer a better description of certain indicators than in BTSF.
- 4) There is a lack of description of the full list of indicators to assess aversion during CAS stunning as well as failure at induction unconsciousness and recovery of consciousness before death following bleeding after CAS in poultry in the training material. More detailed information such as definition, validity, sensitivity and specificity of the indicators, methodology to carry out the assessment and audio-visual support would be of interest to official veterinarians.
- 5) From all the training material revised, only national training material from France is currently covering how the official veterinarians should do checks on animals (*i.e.* frequency, distribution and calculation of sample size).

- 6) The present deliverable provides the opportunity to compare trainings and detect gaps that the EURCAW-Poultry-SFA could possibly address in the future.

5. References

- EFSA (European Food Safety Authority). 2013a. Scientific Opinion on monitoring procedures at slaughterhouses for poultry. *EFSA Journal* 11(12):3521.
- EFSA (European Food Safety Authority). 2013b. Sample size calculation tool for monitoring stunning at slaughter. *EFSA supporting publication* EN-541. 18 pp.
- EFSA (European Food Safety Authority). 2019. Poultry welfare at slaughter: hazards identified, measures proposed. *EFSA Journal* 17(11):5849.

ANNEX 1 Better Training for Safer Food training material

Better Training for Safer Food training material

Here, the titles of the lectures per Better Training for Safer Food (BTSF) edition revised.

2022 e-learning

- Unit 1: Principal references to the legislative requirements (EU legislation; International guidelines)
- Unit 2: Scientific basis for the correct stunning (scientific basis of stunning methods used for poultry; electrical stunning; gas or modified atmosphere stunning; mechanical stunning)
- Unit 3: Main actors for animal welfare in slaughterhouses and Standard Operating Procedures (roles at the slaughterhouse; training and certificate of competence; SOPs and monitoring; the Welfare Quality protocol)
- Unit 4: Animal welfare indicators: practical examples (hazards concerning the pre-stunning process; stunning for slaughter and killing)
- Unit 5: Principal stunning and killing techniques (electrical methods, gas methods and by mechanical methods)
- Unit 6: Killing for depopulation purposes and related operations (action plan; available killing methods for the killing on farm; choose the optimum methodology; controlling good practice; human safety)

2018-2019

- Inspection vs audit as defined in Regulation (EC) No 882/2004: focus on the difference when examining animal welfare (Ref. Council Regulation (EC) N.1099/2009)
- Preparing animals for slaughter (correct unloading avoidance of heat stress in the lairage, feeding and watering): examples from SOPs
- Humane handling (principles, behavioural characteristics, stockman skills, equipment, etc.): examples from SOPs
- How to set up a training course for the slaughterhouse staff and how to assess the quality of such training
- Preparing animals for slaughter (correct unloading avoidance of heat stress in the lairage, feeding and watering)
- Humane Handling (principles, behavioural characteristics, stockman skills, equipment etc.)
- Shackling
- Malpractice in immobilization of birds

- Relevant case studies on official controls on Animal Welfare at arrival, unloading, lairage, moving the animals to the stunning area
- Welfare indicators for developing monitoring procedures at slaughterhouses for poultry stunned using electrical waterbath and gas mixtures (toolbox)
- Welfare indicators for developing monitoring procedures at slaughterhouses for poultry slaughtered without stunning (toolbox)
- Good practices for official veterinarians to conduct an audit on AW at poultry slaughter
- Practical cases on official controls at slaughter (presentation and discussion in plenary session)

2016

- Major outcomes from FVO audit reports on animal welfare at poultry slaughter
- Slaughter of animals: OIE Animal Welfare Standards and perspectives
- Key-actors, their role and interactions: Business Operator, Animal Welfare Officer and Competent Authority
- Animal welfare at slaughter as last ring of the chain: the impact of farming and transport on the welfare conditions of poultry on arrival
- Relevant case studies on: Interaction among Business Operator, Animal Welfare Officer and Competent Authority- the impact of farming and transport on the welfare conditions of poultry on arrival

2014

- EU legislation on the protection of animals at the time of killing: Council Regulation (EC) N. 1099/2009
- Relevant issues and critical factors affecting the implementation of the Council Regulation (EC) N.1099/2009
- Slaughter of animals: OIE Animal Welfare Standards and perspective
- Slaughterhouse key-actors: Business Operator, Animal Welfare Officer and Competent Authority (roles and interactions)
- How to ensure Animal Welfare from unloading to slaughter
- How the design of facilities and equipment's influences the pre-stunning management
- Standard Operating Procedures: aims, application and checks
- Electrical stunning method (poultry, fish, cattle, pigs)
- Mechanical stunning methods
- Gas stunning methods
- Religious slaughter without stunning
- Religious slaughter with stunning
- Animal welfare and Ethics: The ethical logic of Council Regulation 1099/2009
- The relevance of education and training of slaughterhouse personnel

2011-2012

- Relevant issues and critical factors affecting the implementation of the Council Regulation (EC) N. 1099/2009 – Focus on standard slaughter
- Relevant issues and critical factors affecting the implementation of the Council Regulation (EC) N. 1099/2009 – Focus on religious slaughter
- OIE International Animal Welfare Standards
- Gas stunning methods
- Electrical stunning method (poultry, fish, cattle, pigs)
- Mechanical stunning methods
- Religious slaughter without stunning
- Religious slaughter with stunning
- Religious slaughter practices: the approach of Muslim and Jewish communities in implementing EU requirements without stunning
- Religious slaughter practices: the approach of a European country in implement in EU requirements
- Public awareness, raising issues and main concerns on religious slaughter in Europe
- Animal welfare and Ethics: The ethical logic of Council Regulation 1099/2009
- The relevance of education and training of slaughterhouse personnel

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ANNEX 2 National training material

National training material

General information about the National training courses revised per priority area.

Country	Spain
Year	2018
Title	<i>Atordiment per CO2.</i> Stunning by CO2 method.
Duration	Not specified
Objective	Not specified.
Content	Lecture about the stunning by CO2.

Country	Spain
Year	2020
Title	<i>Indicadors de benestar animal en el sacrifici d'aus i de conills.</i> Animal welfare indicators for the slaughter of poultry and rabbits.
Duration	5 h
Objective	To know the indicators of correct stunning, or unconsciousness and death indicators, and authorised stunning methods for each species.
Content	7 lectures are described in the training program, but we only had access to following one: Stunning indicators for rabbits (electric and mechanical methods) and stunning by gas methods in poultry

Country	Spain
Year	2021
Title	<i>Casos pràctics de benestar animal en el sacrifici.</i> Practical examples of animal welfare at slaughter.
Duration	3 h
Objective	To review and publicize the latest news about the animal welfare control plan for slaughterhouse through the presentation of case studies by the official veterinary services.
Content	Three lectures are described in the training program as case-studies, but we only had access to this one: Case-study about actions during a general failure and about the tipping out of the animals into the gas stunning equipment

Country	Italy
Year	2019
Title	<i>Protezione degli animali alla macellazione e all'abbattimento – Regolamento 1099: corso base per responsabili scientifici. Protezione degli avicoli.</i> Protection of animals at slaughter and killing – regulation 1099: basic course for chief scientific officers.
Duration	Not specified.
Objective	Not specified.
Content	One lecture related to poultry welfare at slaughter.

Country	France
Year	2020 (e-learning)
Title	<i>Protection des animaux de boucherie et conditions d'abattage</i> Animal protection in slaughterhouses for poultry and rabbits and associated official controls
Duration	Unknown
Objective	Unknown
Content	Two lectures about poultry welfare at slaughter: one about prerequisites and the other one about the control of loss of consciousness and death confirmation.